

Comparison of Clinical Examination under Anaesthesia, Axillary Ultrasound and Histopathological Examination for Axillary Nodal Staging in Women with Clinically No (Zero) Early Breast Cancer: A Prospective Study

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Abstract:

Objective: The current study aims to compare the sensitivity and specificity of adding examination under anesthesia (EUA) and axillary ultrasound (AUS) to clinical examination (CE) for axillary lymph node staging in women with clinically node negative carcinoma breast.

Material and Methods: This prospective study was conducted on 100 patients coming to the OPD and diagnosed with early breast cancer at tertiary care center from November 2023-October 2024.

Results and Conclusions: This study was conducted on cases of clinically N₀ breast cancer at tertiary care centre. Collected data was analyzed meticulously and results were compared with similar studies done across the world and following conclusions were drawn. Breast cancer involvement of right breast was 50.54 % and left breast was 49.46 %, hence both breasts were almost equally involved. Majority of the patients i.e. 56.98% were found to be overweight. This study showed that, 63.45 % of the cases had lump in upper outer quadrant, which was the most common location. Majority i.e. (52.68 %) had T2 tumour. This study showed that, axillary ultrasound detected metastatic or suspicious lymph node in 16.30%. Only 4.3 % had palpable Lymph node on examination under anesthesia. In this study majority i.e. 82.80% underwent modified radical mastectomy (MRM) and 17.20% underwent breast conservation surgery (BCS).

Keywords: Breast cancer, axillary ultrasound, histopathological examination, axillary nodal staging in women, clinically n₀ (zero) early breast cancer.

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Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women in India, accounts for 14% of all cancers in women. New cases registered: 1, 62,468 (2018) & Deaths: 87,090. In cities like Mumbai, Delhi, Bengaluru, Bhopal, Kolkata, Chennai, Ahmedabad, breast cancer accounts for 25% to 32% of all female cancers, more than 1/4th of all female cancers.

The incidence rates in India begin to rise in the early thirties and peak at ages 50-64 years. Post cancer survival: 60 % (Indian women) Vs 80 % (US) [1]. Cancer survival becomes more difficult in higher stages of its growth more than 50% of Indian women suffer from stage 3 and 4 of breast cancer. Axillary lymph node status is the most important breast cancer prognostic factors and is essential for establishing treatment decisions. Standard surgical care: mastectomy or breast

conserving surgery) with axillary lymph node dissection (ALND). Though SLNB and LAS have proven role in staging of clinically negative axilla there are certain downsides of these modalities. In approximately 70% patients with clinically negative axilla SLNB is negative, other way they are undergoing invasive procedure just because of 30% FNR of clinical examination alone. Axillary ultrasound is being studied as a modality to decrease false negative rate of clinical examination. Clinical examination of the axilla may miss lymph nodes because of contracted state of surrounding muscles.

In present study, we aim to evaluate the sensitivity of both Axillary ultrasound and clinical examination under anesthesia (EUA) in women with clinically N₀ breast cancer to accurately identify women for conservative staging

procedures in the axilla. These will be compared to the gold standard of histopathological examination of axillary lymph nodes.

Aims

Comparison of clinical examination under anesthesia, axillary ultrasound and histopathological examination for axillary nodal staging in women with clinically N₀ (zero) early breast cancer: a prospective study

Objectives

To compare the sensitivity and specificity of adding examination under anesthesia (EUA) and axillary ultrasound (AUS) to clinical examination (CE) for axillary lymph node staging in women with clinically node negative carcinoma breast.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted on 100 patients coming to the OPD and diagnosed with early breast cancer at tertiary care center from November 2023-October 2024.

Inclusion criteria:

- Newly diagnosed breast cancer.
- N₀ on clinical examination.
- Planned for upfront surgery.
- Willing to give consent to participate in the

study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients who have undergone prior axillary surgery or biopsy.
- Those with clinically Node positive disease.

Methodology

All patients fitting into inclusion criteria will undergo USG of the axilla (AUS) by radiologist. Focal cortical thickening, round shape, loss of central echo, disrupted lymph node capsule, and increased intra-nodal vascularisation or atypical vessels were considered as morphologic ultrasound criteria for lymph node malignancy. All patients irrespective of USG finding will undergo examination of axilla under anesthesia prior to surgical procedure (BCT/MRM). Thorough examination of the axilla was done after ensuring proper muscle relaxant had been administered. After that axillary surgery was done.

Considering histopathology of lymph nodes after axillary surgery, sensitivity and specificity of AUS & EUA will be calculated. Patients will be prospectively enrolled in our study between November 2023 to October 2024.

Figure 1: Study design

Statistical Analysis: Evaluation of AUS and EUA in combination with clinical examination was done independently as following:

Table 1:

	Histopathology Positive	Histopathology Negative
Test positive	True positive (a)	False positive (b)
Test Negative	False negative (c)	True negative (d)

Sensitivity: Probability that a test result will be positive when metastasis is present on histopathology (true positive rate). = $a/a+c$

Specificity: Probability that a test result will be negative when the metastasis is not present on histopathology (true negative rate). = $d/b+d$.

Positive predictive value: Probability that the axillary lymph node metastasis is present on histopathology when the test is positive. = $a/a+b$

Negative predictive value: Probability that lymph node metastasis is not present on histopathology when the test is negative. = $d/c+d$

False positive rate: Proportion of people among those responding positive by test, who are actually free of metastasis on histopathology. = $b/a+b$

False negative rate: Proportion of people, among those responding negative on the test, who nevertheless have metastasis on histopathology. = $c/c+d$

Accuracy: Closeness of computations or estimates to the exact or true values. = $a+d/a+b+c+d$

Observation & Results

93 Patients were prospectively enrolled in our study between November 2023 to October 2024.

Figure 2: Observation flow chart

According to above flow chart 93 patients had clinically N₀ breast carcinoma, all patients underwent all 3 procedures i.e. axillary ultrasound, examination under anesthesia and post-operative

histopathological examination of lymph node, which were compared for analysis.

Patient and tumor characteristics:

Table 2: Observation & results table

S. No.	Characteristics	No. (%) of patients
1.	age in years (range) & (median)	(35–80 years) & (53) years
2.	Menopausal status Premenopausal Post-menopausal	38 (40.86%) 55 (59.14%)
3.	Laterality Right Left	47 (50.54%) 46 (49.46%)
4.	Body mass index	

	Underweight (< 18.50) Normal (18.50 – 24.99) Overweight (\geq 30.00)	5 (5.37) 35 (37.6) 53 (56.98)
5.	Quadrant of breast Upper outer Upper inner Lower outer Lower inner Central	59 (63.45%) 07 (7.51 %) 9 (9.68%) 9 (9.68%) 9 (9.68%)
6.	Primary tumor stage T1 T2 T3	22 (23.66%) 49 (52.68%) 22 (23.66%)
7.	AUS Finding: AUS Positive (Metastatic/Suspicious) AUS Negative (Reactive/No node seen)	15 (16.3 %) 78 (83.8 %)
8.	EUA Finding: EUA positive EUA negative (/No node palpable)	4 (4.30 %) 89 (95.7 %)
9.	Type of surgery performed MRM BCS	77 (82.80%) 16 (17.20%)
10.	Histopathology finding: Metastatic Non metastatic	29 (31.20%) 64 (68.80%)

Table 3: Distribution according to age

Age in years	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
<20	00	00
21 – 30	1	1.08
31 – 40	15	16.13
41- 50	30	32.25
51- 60	23	24.73
61- 70	19	20.43
71- 80	05	5.38

Above table shows that in present study out of 93 patients, majority i.e. 30 belonged to age group 41 to 50 years and 23 belonged to age group 51 to 60 years.

Table 4: Distribution according to menstrual status

Menstrual status	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Pre-menopausal	38	40.86
Post-menopausal	55	59.14
Pregnant	00	00

It was observed from above table that, out of total 93 patient's majority (55) i.e. 59.14 % were post-menopausal women and 38 i.e. 40.86 % were premenopausal.

Table 5: Distribution according to laterality of breast

Laterality of breast	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Right	47	50.54
Left	46	49.46

From above table it was observed that out of 93 patients, the breast cancer involved right breast in 47 i.e. 50.54 % and left breast in 46 i.e. 49.46 %, hence both breast were almost equally involved.

Table 6: Distribution according to quadrant involved

Quadrant of breast	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Upper outer quadrant	59	63.45 %.
Lower outer quadrant	09	09.68%
Upper inner quadrant	07	07.51%
Lower inner quadrant	09	09.68%
Central quadrant	09	09.68%

Above table shows that, out of 93 patients 59 i.e. 63.45 % of the cases presented with lump in upper outer quadrant, it was the most common location of the primary tumour in the present study and rest of the quadrants showed fewer incidence.

Table 7: Distribution according to the primary T stage

Primary T stage of tumour	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
T1	22	23.66 %
T2	49	52.68%
T3	22	23.66%

Above table shows that out of 93 patients, majority 49 i.e. 52.68 % were T2 tumour stage and T1 & T2 both being 22 i.e. 23.66 % each.

Table 8: Based on axillary ultrasound (AUS) findings

AUS findings	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
AUS positive (metastatic /suspicious)	15	16.3 %
AUS negative (reactive / no LN seen)	78	83.8 %

In present study 93 clinically N₀ breast cancer patients were enrolled and all patients underwent axillary ultrasound. Above table shows that out of 93 patients axillary ultrasound detected metastatic or suspicious lymph node in 15 i.e. 16.30%. And rest 78 i.e. 83.80 % cases had either reactive lymph node or no lymph node in axilla.

Table 9: Palpable lymph nodes on examination under anesthesia (EUA)

EUA Finding	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
LN Palpable	4	4.30 %
No LN Palpable	89	95.7 %

Out of 93 clinically N₀ breast carcinoma, only 4 i.e. 4.3 % had palpable Lymph node on examination under anesthesia. And rest of the 89 i.e. 95.7% had no palpable Lymph nodes on examination of the axilla under anesthesia.

Table 10: According to the type of surgery performed

Type of surgery	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
MRM	77	82.80%
BCS	16	17.20 %

Out of 93 cases in our study, majority 77 i.e. 82.80% underwent modified radical mastectomy (MRM) and 16 i.e. 17.20 % underwent breast conservation surgery (BCS).

Table 11: Based on Histopathological finding (post-operative)

Histopathological finding	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Metastatic LN	29	31.20 %
Non metastatic LN	64	68.80 %

Out of 93 clinically N₀ breast carcinoma, metastasis to lymph node was found in 29 i.e. 31.20 % and 64 i.e. 68.80 % had no metastasis to lymph node on histopathological examination.

False negative rate of clinical examination alone:

Out of 93 patients with clinically negative axilla, histopathological examination revealed metastatic lymph node in 31.20%. Hence clinical examination alone had FNR of 31.20 %.

On axillary ultrasonography examination detected in 15 patients.
suspicious or metastatic lymph node in axilla were

Table 12: AUS in combination with clinical examination versus HPR of LN: statistics

CE + AUS Finding	Histopathology positive (29)	Histopathology negative (64)	
CE + AUS Positive (15)	13 (a)	2 (b)	
CE+ AUS Negative (78)	16 (c)	62 (d)	
Statistic	Calculation	Value	95% CI
Sensitivity	$13/(13+16) = 13/29$	44.83%	26.45% to 64.31%
Specificity	$62/(2+62) = 62/64$	96.88%	89.16% to 99.62%
Positive Predictive Value	$13/(13+2) = 13/15$	86.67%	61.04% to 96.42%
True negative (NPV)	$62/(16+62) = 62/78$	79.49%	73.57% to 84.36%
False negative rate (FNR)	$16/(16+62) = 16/78$	20.51%	15.64-26.43%
False positive rate (FPR)	$02/(2+13) = 2/15$	13.33%	3.67-38.35%
Accuracy	$(13+62)/(13+2+16+62) = 75/93$	80.65%	71.15% to 88.11%

From above table it is apparent that adding axillary ultrasound to clinical examination decreases false negative rate to 20.51% from 31.20% for clinical examination alone i.e. (FNR of CE+AUS was 20.51% & FNR of CE alone was 31.20%) which was statistically not significant. Sensitivity of axillary ultrasound in identifying metastatic lymph

nodes was 44.83%. Specificity of the axillary ultrasound for identification of metastatic lymph node was 96.88%. Due to FPR of 13.33% i.e. 1/6 of the patients of the patients labelled with axillary lymph node metastasis by combined Clinical examination and axillary ultrasound will undergo unnecessary axillary clearance.

Table 13: Clinical examination in combination with EUA versus HPR of LN: statistics

CE + EUA Finding	Histopathology Positive (29)	Histopathology negative (64)
CE + EUA Positive (4)	2 (a)	2 (b)
CE + EUA Negative (89)	27 (c)	62 (d)

Statistic	Calculation	Value	95% CI
Sensitivity	$2/(2+27) = 2/29$	6.90%	0.85% to 22.77%
Specificity	$62/(62+2) = 62/64$	96.88%	89.16% to 99.62%
Positive predictive value (PPV)	$2/(2+2) = 2/4$	50.00%	12.90% to 87.10%
True negative (NPV)	$62/(62+27) = 62/89$	69.66%	67.32% to 71.90%
False negative rate (FNR)	$27/(27+62) = 27/89$	30.33%	28.1-32.68%
False positive rate (FPR)	$2/(2+2) = 2/4$	50%	12.9-87.10%
Accuracy	$(2+62)/(2+27+2+62) = 64/93$	68.82%	58.37% to 78.02%

It is clear from above table that, adding examination under anesthesia to decrease FNR of clinical examination was also futile.

FNR of EUA combined with CE was 30.33% (on 95 % confidence interval, with range 28.1 to 32.68%) which was not significantly lower than FNR of CE alone i.e.31.20%. Sensitivity of

clinical examination under anesthesia in detecting axillary lymph node was 6.9 % only which was very subtle clinically. And specificity was 96.88%.

Due to FPR of 50%, half of the patients labelled with axillary lymph node metastasis by combined CE and EUA will undergo unnecessary axillary clearance.

Table 14: Clinical examination combined with both AUS and EUA.

CE + AUS + EUA combined	Histopathology Positive (29)	Histopathology negative (64)
Test positive (15)	13 (a)	2 (b)
Test negative (78)	16 (c)	62 (d)

Statistic	Calculation	Value	95% ci
Sensitivity	$13/(13+16) = 13/29$	44.83%	26.45% to 64.31%
Specificity	$62/(2+62) = 62/64$	96.88%	89.16% to 99.62%
Positive Predictive Value	$13/(13+2) = 13/15$	86.67%	61.04% to 96.42%
True negative (NPV)	$62/(16+62) = 62/78$	79.49%	73.57% to 84.36%
False negative rate (FNR)	$16/(16+62) = 16/78$	20.51%	15.64-26.43%
False positive rate (FPR)	$02/(2+13) = 2/15$	13.33%	3.67-38.35%
Accuracy	$(13+62)/(13+2+16+62) = 75/93$	80.65%	71.15% to 88.11%

Adding both axillary ultrasound and examination under anesthesia to clinical examination, did not change results of clinical examination combined

with axillary ultrasound, because both patients with positive examination under anesthesia were positive on axillary ultrasound also.

Table 15: Comparison of various tests

Statistic	Clinical examination	Clinical examination + AUS	Clinical examination + EUA	Clinical examination + AUS + EUA
Sensitivity	-	44.82 %	6.89 %	44.82 %
Specificity	-	96.87 %	96.87 %	96.87 %
NPV	-	79.48 %	69.66 %	79.48 %
FNR	31.20 %	20.51 %	30.33 %	20.51 %
FPR	-	13.33 %	50%	13.33 %
Accuracy	-	80.64 %	68.8 %	80.64 %

From above table it is clear that FNR of clinical examination alone 31.20 % decreases to 20.51% adding axillary ultrasonography to clinical examination. FNR of clinical examination alone 31.20% did not change significantly on adding examination under anesthesia alone 30.33%.

The FNR by EUA combined with CE 30.33 % (95% CI, 28.1 to 32.68%) versus FNR by CE combined with AUS 20.51 % (95%CI, 15.64 to 26.43%) was not statistically significant.

FPR of CE and EUA combination was 50% (95 % - CI, 12.9-87.10%), which was higher than CE combined with AUS 13.33 % (95 % CI, 3.58-38.96%) and was statistically significant. FPR was lowest for combination of CE and AUS.

Sensitivity of AUS was 44.82 %, adding EUA to AUS did not change the sensitivity.

Whereas adding only EUA to CE sensitivity was very less i.e.6.89 %. Specificity is same with adding both AUS & EUA to CE

Discussion

In a study by Nashwan k et al, majority were between age group 28 – 72 years. [2]

In a study by J. S. Vaidya et al, the median age group affected by clinically N₀ breast cancer was 45 years.[3] In a study by J. Bonnema et al, age group range was 30 to 80 years & median age involved was 57 years.[4] In a study by Jaun Harrada et al, median age group involving was 47 years.[5] In the present study majority of the patients belonged to age group 41 to 50 years and next 51 to 60 years, And median age of involvement of clinically NO breast cancer was 53 years, which is greater than study by J. S. Vaidya et al & Jaun Harrada et al. which were 45 & 47 years respectively. Whereas, comparable to study by J. Bonnema et al which had 57 years as median age group.

In a study by Hassan A Hataum et al, postmenopausal women were more involved than premenopausal i.e. 54.4 % and 45.6 % respectively.[6] A study by Bedrosian et al, also

found that postmenopausal women were more affected than premenopausal.[7] In the present study it was observed that, among 93 cases postmenopausal women were 59.14 % and premenopausal were 40.86 %. In a study by Nashwan k et al, it was seen that the left side breast was involved more than right side i.e. 46.67 % and 42.23 % respectively.[2]

In a study by Kubiley et al, they observed that involvement of breast was almost equal on both sides with slight preponderance of right breast.[8]

In the present study was observed that the right breast was involves 50.54 % and left breast involves 49.46 % of cases, which is similar to study by Kubiley et al. [8]

In a study by Kubiley et al, they observed that Upper outer quadrant was most commonly involved i.e. 44.19% followed by upper inner quadrant (25.59 %) followed by lower outer quadrant (12.8%) then lower inner and central quadrant.[8]

In a study by Sabahtinn et al, it was observed that upper outer quadrant was most frequently involved (64.4%).[9]

In the present study, upper outer quadrant was most commonly involved i.e. 63.45% followed by lower inner and lower outer and central quadrant equally involved with 9.68 % each, & upper inner quadrant was least common i.e. 7.51 %.

Comparison shows that, maximum tumours were present in upper outer quadrant of breast. In a study by Nashwan k et al, 50 % were T2 stage followed by T1 and T3.[2]

In a study by Hassan A Hatoum et al, 58.9 % were T2 stage then T1 (25.6%).[6] In a study by J Bonnema et al, 51% were T1 stage followed by T2 stage.[4] In the Present study 52.68 % were T2 stage then T1 and T3, 23.66% each.

A similar study by J Bedrosian et al, found axillary ultrasound suggestive of metastatic node in 14 % cases of clinically N₀ breast cancer and negative in 86 % cases.[7] a study by J Bonnema et al, found

metastatic lymph node in 62 % and negative in 38% [4].

In the present study axillary ultrasound was positive in 16.3% of cases of clinically N₀ breast carcinoma. And axillary ultrasound did not detect significant metastatic node in 83.8 % of cases which was similar to study by J Bedrosian et al.

In a study by Kamalesh Verma et al, it was observed that on examination under anesthesia lymph node was palpable in 3.9% of cases and negative in 96.1% of cases.

In the present study out of 93 cases of clinically N₀ breast carcinoma, we had found palpable Lymph node on examination under anesthesia in 4 i.e. 4.3 % of the cases and rest of the 89 i.e. 95.7% cases had no palpable Lymph nodes on examination of the axilla under anesthesia which is similar to study by Kamalesh et al.

In a study by Hassan A et al, found that MRM was done in 84.7% cases and BCS was done in 15.3% cases.

In a study by Nashwan k et al, and Soledal alvarez et al found MRM was done more frequently than BCS. In the present study MRM was done in 82.80% cases and BCS was done in 17.20% cases. In a study by V parmar et al,[10] and Bassi k et al [11] metastatic lymph node were detected in 30 % and 31.5 % cases of clinically N₀ breast cancer.

In a study by Nashwan et al found metastatic lymph node in 39 % of cases.[2] In a study by Bedrosian et al, found histopathology positive in 22% cases.

In a study by J Bonnema et al, found lymph node metastasis in 41% cases.[4] In present study we found that lymph node metastasis was found in 31.20% cases and

No lymph node metastasis was found in 68.80% cases which was comparable to above studies.

Hence from above all tables and statistics it has been observed that the Clinical examination of axilla is false negative in a third of cases, leading to

need for invasive methods in form of sentinel lymph node biopsy, axillary sampling or axillary clearance to accurately stage the axilla. In this study we attempted to stage the axilla by non-invasive means like axillary ultrasound, examination under anesthesia and compared their accuracy with gold standard of histopathological examination (HPE).

False -ve rate of clinical examination: Study by Tanis PJ et al. showed sentinel nodes contain tumor cells in approximately 40% of patients (12).

Jorien Bonnema et al. detected metastatic lymph node in 62 axilla on histopathological examination of sentinel lymph node biopsy/axillary clearance specimen out of 150 clinically negative axilla, giving rise to 41.3% FNR for clinical examination.

A study by Malcolm et al found false negative rate of 28.8 % of clinical examination alone.

In present study 29 patients were detected with metastatic lymph node on HPE, leading to FNR of 31.20% for clinical examination which is comparable to Malcom et al and lower than that of study by Tanis PJ et al and J Bonnema et al.

Diagnostic criteria on AUS: Two sonographic criteria can be used to diagnose a node as metastatic: size (> 5mm) and morphology (round, hypo echoic, with loss of central hilum, eccentric cortical hypertrophy). In this study we used both criteria to look for metastatic lymph node in axilla. Systematic review by Soledad Alvarez showed that morphological criteria are more sensitive (48.4% versus 28.4%) and specific (96.5% versus 49.7%) than size criteria [13].

A study by J S Vaidya et al showed axillary ultrasound with specificity of 90 % and positive predictive value of 90% [3]. In the present study the AUS was 44.83% sensitive and 96.88% specific and PPV of 86.67%.

AUS combined with clinical examination: Our results are similar to earlier studies, that CE combined with AUS is better than CE alone in the detection of axillary nodal metastases.

Table 16: correlation of various studies

Study	No. of patients	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	NPV (%)	Accuracy (%)
Current study	93	44.82	96.87	79.48	80.64
Bonnema J et al. (1997) [4]	148	36.0	95.0	63.0	67.0
Bedrosian et al. (2003) [7]	208	26.4	90.9	78.3	-
J S Vaidya et al [3]	200	82	90	76	-
Soledal et al [13]	170	48.8	97.3	80	85.4
Kubilay et al [8]	172	58	91.6	73	-

In our study, sensitivity of CE combined with AUS was 44.82%. Thus CE combined with AUS was helpful to pick up 44.82% of patients with axillary

metastasis, who were labelled negative for metastases by clinical examination alone.

Sensitivity of CE combined with AUS as per our study is comparable with that of Soledal et al & higher than study by Bedrosian et al & Bonnema J et al. Specificity of CE combined with AUS, in our study was similar to most of the studies.

NPV of combined CE and AUS in our study was 79.48 which is similar to that found in soledal et al and Bedrosian et al and it was slightly higher than that found in Bonnema J et al, J S Vaidya et al and Kubilay et al. Accuracy of CE combined with AUS in our study was higher than study by Bonnema J et al (54.9% versus 67.0%) and lower than that of Soledal et al.

Accuracy of clinical examination combined with EUA: Other modality tested for non-invasive staging of axilla in our study is examination under anesthesia (EUA). Though sensitivity of EUA was low in our study (6.89%), it was associated with high specificity (96.87%). Combining EUA to CE is not much helpful in bringing down FNR of CE (30.33% from 31.20%). Associated with FPR of 50%, patient labeled to have metastatic axillary lymph node by EUA will have 50% probability of undergoing unnecessary axillary clearance. In a similar study by Kamalesh verma et al the sensitivity of examination under anesthesia was 5.9 % and specificity was 97.1%. On adding EUA to CE they could bring FNR of CE to 32.6% from 33.3% which was not much of significance.

Accuracy of clinical examination combined with both AUS and EUA: Adding both AUS and EUA to clinical examination, does not change results of clinical examination combined with AUS alone, because both patients with positive EUA were positive on AUS also. Because of low overall yield of EUA, adding EUA to AUS is not going to bring down false positive rate of AUS.

Impact of various modalities on extent of axillary surgery: Deurloo et al. studied the ability of preoperative ultrasonography to reduce the number of patients required to undergo sentinel lymph node biopsy and also reducing the FNR of SNB. In his study using ultrasound and FNA, SLNB was avoided in 37 out of 268 patients (14%). Ying zhu et al found an unnecessary axillary dissection in 36.1 % of cases. Holly Caretta-Weyer et al, found that about 12 % of cases in a cohort underwent unnecessary axillary clearance.

According to our results AUS will label 16.13% axilla positive (15 out of 93) which will result in avoiding SLNB/AS in them, and they can directly go for AC. But it is also associated with a FPR of 13.33%, whereby, 2 out of 93 patients (2.15%) will undergo unnecessary axillary surgery. Having prior knowledge of disease in lymph node by adding an axillary ultrasound guided FNA, the FPR of AUS can be brought down and unnecessary AC can be avoided. Using AUS guided FNA we should be

able to identify true positive cases (n=13), thus SLNB/AS may be avoided in 13.97% cases (13 out of 93) as also, 2/93 patients (2.15%) cases will be spared from morbidity of unnecessary axillary clearance. Combining CE with EUA will avoid SLNB in only 3.9% of patients and thus is clinically not relevant. Combining CE with both EUA and AUS will have same impact as of combined CE and AUS.

Impact of clinicopathological factors on performance of AUS:

A study by Bedrosian et al. showed that no significant clinicopathologic criteria were found to impact sensitivity of ultrasonography. A study by Kubilay Ertan et al. showed that sensitivity and specificity of axillary ultrasound were impacted by tumor size, suspicious lymph node on axillary palpation, number of affected lymph nodes and distant metastases. We could not analyze the impact of clinic pathological factors on the sensitivity and specificity of AUS, due to limited sample size.

Limitations of the Study

Number of patients included in our study is small. So the results of our study cannot be generalized to overall population of clinically node negative carcinoma breast patients.

No control group involved in the study.

Patients were considered to have metastatic lymph node on the basis of sonography features only. FNA confirmation of AUS findings was not included in the study.

Conclusion

On the basis of this study, we conclude that, Sensitivity and specificity of AUS remains same despite combining it with EUA and false negative rate of clinical examination cannot be decreased significantly despite combining it with AUS, EUA or both. No imaging technique until now has been successful enough to replace histopathological examination. There is no impact on number of sentinel lymph node biopsy/Axillary sampling/axillary clearance performed, by combining CE with AUS, EUA or both.

Examination under anesthesia though being very less sensitive for metastatic lymph node is highly specific for node negative status, but considering the high false positive rate of EUA alone we conclude it does not add any benefit to the CE and AUS. AUS guided FNAC in AUS positive lymph nodes though an option needs further studies. Till date sentinel lymph node biopsy/ low axillary sampling is essential in clinically node negative patients.

Reference

1. Ferlay J BF, Pisani P, Parkin DM. GLOBOCAN 2000: Cancer Incidence, Mortality and Prevalence Worldwide, Version 1.0. 2001.
2. Nashwan K. Mahjob, Faris H. Raoof. Clinical versus histopathological staging of axillary lymph node, in breast cancer patients. *Ann coll Med Mosul* 2013; 59-64.
3. Vaidya JS, Vyas JJ, Thakur MH, Khandelwal KC, Mitra I. Role of ultrasonography to detect axillary node involvement in operable breast cancer. *Eur J Surg Oncol* 1996; 22:140–143.
4. Bonnema J, van Geel AN, van Ooijen B, et al. Ultrasound- guided aspiration biopsy for detection of nonpalpable axillary node metastases in breast cancer patients: new diagnostic method. *World J Surg* 1997; 21:270–274.
5. J Herrada, R B Iyer, E N Atkinson, et al. Relative value of physical examination, mammography, and breast sonography in evaluating the size of the primary tumor and regional lymph node metastases in women receiving neoadjuvant chemotherapy for locally advanced breast carcinoma. *Clin Cancer Res* 1997; 3:1565-1569.
6. Hassan A. Hatoum, Faek R. Jamali. Ratio Between Positive Lymph Nodes and Total Excised Axillary Lymph Nodes as an Independent Prognostic Factor for Overall Survival in Patients with Nonmetastatic Lymph Node-Positive Breast Cancer. *Indian J Surg Oncol* (October– December 2010) 1(4):305–312.
7. Bedrosian I, Bedi D, Kuerer HM, et al. Impact of clinicopathological factors on sensitivity of axillary ultrasonography in the detection of axillary nodal metastases in patients with breast cancer. *Ann Surg Oncol* 2003; 10:1025–1030.
8. Kubilay Ertan, Christina Linsler, and Alexander di Liberto, et al. Axillary Ultrasound for Breast cancer staging: an Attempt to identify clinical/Histopathological Factors Impacting Diagnostic performance; *Breast Cancer: Basic and Clinical Research* 2013;7 35–40.
9. Sabahattin Aslan, Bahadir Cetin et al. Level 3 lymph node involvement in breast carcinoma. *Turkish journal of cancer* 2007; 37.3:109-13
10. V. Parmar, R. Hawaldar, N.S. Nair et al. Sentinel node biopsy versus low axillary sampling in women with clinically node negative operable breast cancer. *The Breast* 22 (2013) 1081 – 1086.
11. Bassi KK, Seenu V, Srivastava A, AI Sharana N. Role of axillary sampling in the era of sentinel lymph node biopsy: A critical review. *Indian j cancer* 2012; 49: 66-73.
12. Drug & diseases – Oncology Breast cancer. Practice essentials. Medscape.
13. Soledad Alvarez, Enrique Anorbe, Pilar Alcorta et al. Role of sonography in the diagnosis of axillary lymph node metastases in breast cancer: A systematic review. *AJR* (2006) 186: 1342-1348.